

SOTECIN

FACTORY

D2.1 Report on low-carbon and circular industrial value chains

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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
CE	Circular Economy
CSC	Circular Supply Chain
CSCM	Circular Supply Chain Management
SC	Supply Chain
SCM	Supply Chain Management
EoL	End-of-Life

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the work developed in T2.1 for the definition of the Principles of the SoTeIn Factory to support low-carbon and circular industrial value chains. This document is a summarized version of the deliverable, which will be updated after a scientific publication of its results.

In particular, in this task we have investigated models available in literature and we have developed a 2-level framework for strategically link the foundational concepts of the project and for operative support to supply chain (SC) processes.

On one hand, the overall conceptualisation of the new framework was based on defining relationships between the different dimensions of the SoTeIn Factory with particular focus on how Circular Economy (CE) is linked to the concept of resilience and how it can be supported by technologies and collaboration. On the other hand, the operational framework is based on the analysis of the SC processes and aims to enhance: i) the role of the CE strategies along the SC processes; ii) the role of different set of stakeholders and how to manage the relationships between businesses and social innovators to blend market-based principles and new collaboration mechanisms; iii) organization of SC processes in deploying the CE strategies.

The conceptual and operational frameworks were designed in such a way to define mechanisms where social and industrial actors can pool resources through collaborative mechanisms, including knowledge, creativity and technologies. Special attention was given to different trust building mechanisms and to the use of technologies to support these. Moreover, this deliverable aims to define how the SoTeIn Factory framework can increase our understanding of how CE can help companies to face resilience, defined as the capability to face disruptive events, while improving social, environmental, and economic outcomes of the industrial value chains.

After the introduction, section 2 is related to the method used in the task, while section 3 and 4 summarise the most important findings related to the dimensions we are analysing namely CE, resilience and their link, technologies and their role in enabling CE, and collaboration. Section 5 describes the SoTeIn Factory framework giving the overall picture both of the conceptual and the operational models. Section 6 summarises the most important findings related to the 4 value chains selected for this project, namely textile, agrifood, plastic and packaging, shortly describing the value chains and describing some of the challenges found in literature and from projects already developed by consortium partners. Section 7 present the main conclusions of this deliverable.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope of deliverable

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the work developed in T2.1 for the definition of the Principles of the SoTeIn Factory to support low-carbon and circular industrial value chains.

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1.2 Contribution to other WPs

The work in T2.1 is interlinked to all the tasks in WP2 and forms an important foundation for the work in WP3. In particular, for what concerns activities in WP2, the conceptual model developed in T2.1 can be used as a backbone for the definition of the features of the business models in T2.3 and can also be used to inform aspects of the impact assessment framework to be developed in T2.4. T2.1 also benefited from the outcomes of the T2.2 particularly by including different collaborative frameworks to be instantiated in CE.

For what concerns WP3, T2.1 activities will support WP3 by providing content and definitions related to CE and resilience so that it will facilitate the definition of the missions and challenges for each of the selected value chains. A summary of the concepts studied in this task has been used during the presentations in the workshops organised by the Impact hubs for stakeholders of the related value chains and will be used also in the next months for guiding the identification of the challenges and definition of the two open calls.

1.3 Contribution to other deliverables

D2.4: Report on Impact assessment framework and D3.1: Value Chain Challenges

2. METHODOLOGY

The work in T2.1 is designed as an exploratory study and helps to define the main concepts related to Low-Carbon and Circular Industrial Value Chains; to seek new insights; to ask questions and to assess these phenomena in a new light. In this task, qualitative methods are used for collecting and analysing data from literature. Secondary data have also been collected from published articles in scientific journals, reports, online search, and books. The main goal is to contribute to knowledge by defining a new framework to help organisations in the context of circular value chain transformation. Critical literature review has been undertaken to develop the structure of the framework, to assess which variables should be considered, and how the variables are interlinked. Best practices and real-life case studies have been collected both from secondary data and from the project partners as a way to gain in depth knowledge of the research context and in particular of how the value chains are facing challenges for CE in terms of processes and actors involved. The approach was based on periodic reporting with partners and in particular in participating to the workshops organised with the Impact Hubs where different stakeholders were involved. In this way, it was possible to have a mutual benefit because the theoretical work in this task could support the identification of open issues in terms of circular value chain transformation and with the definition of the missions. Moreover, this framework will be used as a guideline to identify the Value Chain Challenges (D3.1).

Figure 1: Overall methodology

3. DEFINITION OF CIRCULARITY CONCEPTS

This section has been summarized and it will be updated after a scientific publication.

Currently, sustainability is a buzzword, being widely discussed both in the academic literature, as well as in the business world (de Angelis et al., 2018; Farooque et al., 2019). Given the unsustainability of the current linear economic model of production and consumption (take-make-dispose), the concept of circular economy (CE) has recently gained traction as one of the best alternatives to move towards a more sustainable, low-carbon and competitive economy (de Angelis et al., 2018; Farooque et al., 2019; García-Quevedo et al., 2020). To transition towards a more circular economy requires low-carbon energy inputs and reducing the dependence on finite natural resources, thus ensuring long-term resilience of the global economic systems (Farooque et al., 2019; García-Quevedo et al., 2020; Tan & Lamers, 2021). Low-carbon strategies (i.e., strategies to mitigate climate change by reducing carbon emissions to the atmosphere) will support the application of the CE concept, alongside with dematerialization strategies (Winans et al., 2017).

At the organizational level, the transition to a CE requires changing the company's business model, to meet an equilibrium between the environment and the economy. In this way, it will be possible to produce profitable products, while minimizing waste or leaking energy, through the development of closed-loop systems (Awan et al., 2022; Brennan et al., 2015; Geissdoerfer et al., 2017; Winans et al., 2017). The closed-loop model of production systems is supported by reverse logistics (de Giovanni, 2022; de Lima et al., 2021). In this way, we understand that the CE concept is not new, but it is one that has been increasingly gaining attention from businesses and policymakers, due to the mounting evidence of environmental degradation provoked by the linear economy (de Angelis et al., 2018; de Lima et al., 2021; Lahane et al., 2020).

The most prominent CE definition, widely adopted in the literature, is the one provided by The Ellen MacArthur Foundation (Farooque et al., 2019; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018; Kirchherr et al., 2017), that defines it as **an economy that is restorative and regenerative by design, based on three principles: designing out waste and pollution, keeping products and materials in use and regenerating natural systems** (EMF, 2019). This definition conveys the idea that “waste is food”, i.e., all products and materials used can become, at the end of their lifecycle, in an input for new products (Fischer & Pascucci, 2017).

However, in this transition from a linear to a CE, one of the challenges is to overcome uncertainties related to inter-firm relationships and to the design of materials and processes (Fischer & Pascucci, 2017). Consequently, it will inspire circular supply chains (CSCs). In fact, the SC plays a key role in the transition to a CE, especially in implementing low-carbon strategies and circularity practices (de Angelis et al., 2018). CSCs aim at reducing the environmental impacts of linear economy by incorporating circular thinking into SCs' operations, actors and processes (de Angelis et al., 2018; de Lima et al., 2021; Farooque et al., 2019).

The incorporation of circular thinking in the supply chain management (SCM) is called circular supply chain management (CSCM) (de Angelis et al., 2018; Farooque et al., 2019). CSCM has both restorative cycles of technical materials and regenerative cycles of biological materials that are done systematically, wherein the goal is to achieve a zero-waste economy through the recovery of value from what was traditionally called waste (Farooque et al., 2019). Farooque et al. (2019, p.884) presents the following CSCM definition: “*the integration of circular thinking into the management of the supply chain and its surrounding industrial and natural ecosystems. It systematically restores technical materials and regenerates biological materials toward a zero-waste vision through system-wide innovation in business models and supply chain functions from product/service design to end-of-*

life and waste management, involving all stakeholders in a product/service lifecycle including parts/product manufacturers, service providers, consumers, and users”.

Therefore, we conclude that when adopting a CSC, companies need to implement a set of CE practices, namely the R strategies, such as repair, reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishing, recycling (de Lima et al., 2021; Kalmykova et al., 2018; Kirchherr et al., 2017).

The transition to circular value chains requires a holistic approach, improving the current business models as well as developing new ones (Reike et al., 2018; Suárez-Eiroa et al, 2021). In addition to their clear contribution to environmental sustainability, circular value chain models also show great potential to contribute to economic (e.g. reducing costs with raw material) and social aspects (e.g. creating new jobs) as well as to the resilience of value chains (e.g. reducing “traditional” suppliers’ dependencies) (de Angelis et al., 2018; de Lima et al., 2021; Farooque et al., 2019).

In conclusion, our strategy will focus on the analysis of the Rs, namely the 10Rs (refuse, rethink, reduce, reuse, repair, refurbish, remanufacture, repurpose, recycle, recover), since these CE strategies are core to achieving low-carbon and circular value chains. The role of the Rs in circular value chains will be discussed in the following section.

3.1 Role of Rs – Circularity R’s-based framework

This section was removed for confidentiality purposes. It will be updated after a scientific publication.

3.1.1. R0 – Refuse

3.1.2. R1 - Rethink

3.1.3. R2 - Reduce

3.1.4. R3 - Reuse

3.1.5. R4 - Repair

3.1.6. R5 - Refurbish

3.1.7. R6 - Remanufacture

3.1.8. R7 - Repurpose

3.1.9. R8 - Recycle

3.1.10. R9 - Recover

3.2 Prioritisation of the Rs strategies

This sections was removed for confidentiality purposes. It will be updated after a scientific publication.

3.3 Barriers and Challenges for CE implementation

Although circular models are emerging as a priority to companies (oftentimes reflecting the consumers behaviour), the transition from linear supply chains to more circular ones is not an easy task. Many barriers and challenges associated with the implementation of circular supply chains have

been addressed in the literature (Fischer & Pascucci, 2017). Moreover, many strategies have not been properly tested yet in many sectors, generating uncertainties about the processes and results.

The main barriers identified in the literature are listed in Table 1, classified by different types: strategic and operational uncertainties; technical; institutional/regulatory; and financial barriers. These types were listed as the most common difficulties faced by companies in the adoption of circular strategies (Jesus et. al, 2018).

Table 1. Main barriers and challenges for circular economy implementation

Type of barrier/challenge	Description	References
Strategic and operational uncertainties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High levels of uncertainty related to the quantity and quality of materials available from circular channels/suppliers; • Lack of supply chain visibility (including track and trace) prevents companies from knowing in detail the life cycle of products and components that are part of their production process; • Lack of information to predict customer/market demands and behaviors related to products derived from circular strategies • Difficulties in aligning circular practices with commercial strategies; • Lack of cross-sectorial collaboration hampers the use of discarded products and/or components from one sector in the production processes of other sectors. 	Peng et al. (2020); de Lima, Seuring & Sauer (2021).
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absence of appropriate technology (both for track products and components during their life cycle and to support new production systems in the context of the different Rs); • Low technical skills to deal with the different Rs strategies; • Lack of efficient collection and sorting schemes. 	De Jesus & Mendonça (2018); Dissanayake & Weerasinghe (2021).
Institutional / Regulatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of government support and incentives; • Lack of standards and/or best practices (benchmark) to define the contracts and agreements among companies in the adoption of a circular perspective; • Lack of regulation and environmental laws; • Lack of appropriate company policies. 	Lahane et al (2020); de Lima, Seuring & Sauer (2021); Dissanayake & Weerasinghe (2021);
Financial / Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs to implement new technologies to support circularity; • Lack of financial resources; • Many stakeholders and activities; 	De Jesus & Mendonça (2018); Lahane et al., (2020); Ki, Chong & Ha-Brookshire (2020),

Type of barrier/challenge	Description	References
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider the waste a cost and not a resource to close the loop; • Lack of market opportunities for recycled materials. 	Sandvik & Stubbs (2019); Dissanayake & Weerasinghe (2021)
Cultural / Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to changes; • Habits of consumption; • Lack of consumer interest. 	De Jesus & Mendonça (2018); Kirchherr et al., (2018).
Workforce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of sufficient knowledge; • Lack of qualified personnel; • Resistance to changes; • Lack of awareness regarding sustainability and circularity. 	De Jesus & Mendonça (2018); Dissanayake & Weerasinghe, (2021)

4. CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND RESILIENCE

The declining state of the environment raises substantial concerns about how current industrial systems are eroding the resilience of social and industrial systems. Resilience is defined as the ability of companies and generally ecosystems to cope with shocks and disturbances that may lead to non-linear and transformative change (Folke et al., 2010). Resource extraction, land-use changes, unexpected health crisis, resource scarcity are just some of the causes that are pushing systems towards new models where circular economy can play a role (Kennedy & Linnenluecke, 2022 2022).

Management studies bridging the CE and resilience are sparse, leaving critical questions unanswered, including how pursuing the CE may influence firm, industry and social-ecological resilience and how principles of resilience may be integrated into CE practices (Kennedy & Linnenluecke, 2022). Management research on the CE shares some aspects with management research on resilience (e.g., both research streams seek to develop managerial solutions to address complex environmental challenges), but they have developed largely independently and have substantial differences in focus and implications for key managerial practices. CE practices are implicitly assumed to build social-ecological system resilience at multiple levels, but the conceptual or empirical research that supports this assumption through explicitly studying the areas of compatibility and contestation of the two domains is lacking.

Models on CE are becoming more and more important, but as they are not engaging with the concept of resilience more deeply, there is the risk that CE research focuses on solution models that may lead to suboptimal outcomes for resilience and may even increase the vulnerability of firms, industries and social-ecological systems. For instance, practices that seek to increase resource efficiencies in the CE may remove the buffers, diversity and slack resources needed to withstand and adapt to shocks and disturbances. For this reason we aim to study a new conceptual framework that connects CE and resilience at multiple levels. Our research contributes by providing an explicit foundation for companies and scholars on the integration of the concepts of CE with resilience perspective.

We analyse these two fields and draw distinctions between their principles and business practices. Furthermore, we offer an examination of the limited body of literature that has sought to connect the two fields to date. Secondly, our research agenda helps to focus the attention of management scholars to the critical intersections between the CE and resilience by identifying if there is a trade-off between the 2 areas of study.

4.1 The Circular Economy link to Resilience

Managing resilience requires embracing a continually changing world and building adaptive and transformative capacities to understand, anticipate and respond to various types of disruptions and change (Walker & Salt, 2006). Managers must be sensitive to weak signals from the systems in which their company works to avoid adverse outcomes at the firm, industry or social-ecological system level (Williams et al., 2021). However, sudden changes to internal processes or external shocks and disturbances can cause critical adaptation limits to be exceeded (i.e., an organisation or system cannot adapt fast enough to continue with business-as-usual), forcing organisations and broader systems to either decline or transform (Kennedy & Linnenluecke, 2022).

Practices for building resilience vary depending on the level (firm, industry, social-ecological systems) at which resilience is meant to be achieved. At the organisational level, it is necessary to study how companies can build internal resilience through high reliability (i.e., improving their abilities to discover and correct failures before they happen). Failure prediction is not only for organisations that need to operate with high levels of reliability, such as hospitals, air traffic controllers or nuclear power plants, but rather also manufacturing companies at any level are applying this kind of strategy as a way to make the system resilient (Brandon-Jones et al., 2014). Organisations can build resilient strategies to exogenous change through adaptable business models, rapid responses and the establishment of resilient supply chains (Kennedy & Linnenluecke, 2022). As an example of practices for resilience is the implementation of slack and buffer capacities within a firm and across its supply chain, avoiding tight coupling and high levels of interconnectedness that can lead to cascading or escalating failures within or across firms. Such capacities can be achieved through diversification (e.g., across supplier/buyer networks, markets and manufacturing sites) and redundancy (e.g., of structures, relationships and personnel), which enable functions to continue in times of adversity.

Researchers are increasingly looking beyond the firm's boundaries to understand the intersection between firms and the resilience of larger systems within which the firm is embedded. An industry-wide lens reveals how firms are interdependent and provides opportunities for business practices that aim to strengthen entire economic sectors. Other research has highlighted the importance of social networks, as well as access to financial and human resources in order to react quickly (Nikookar et al., 2022).

There are also works where resilience addresses the structural elements dealing with changes, linking it to the ability to change toward more circular and sustainable systems (Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2021). Other works relate to the integrations of resilience thinking and CE (Fabbricatti and Biancamano, 2019), proposing a policy framework to manage urban landscapes by integrating the concepts of circularity, productivity and resilience, or connecting several solutions to face waste, energy, water, and pollution challenges into a smart, resilient, sustainable and CE (Fan et al., 2019).

Despite the lack of a formal and explicit integration of CE and resilience, the CE umbrella has progressively incorporated different elements from the resilience-thinking paradigm (Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2021) where multi-stakeholder partnerships are required to advance CE practices and business models (Schroeder et al., 2019) and where resilience becomes a key concern to help interconnections and interdependences when aiming at CE and sustainability.

4.2 Technologies as enabler of Circular Economy

Technologies have been largely recognized as an important enabler of the implementation of circular strategies. Table 2 presents the potential contribution of the main digital technologies to the development of circular supply chain models found in the literature.

Table 2. Contribution of digital technologies to circular supply chains

Technology	Potential contribution	References
Big Data and Advanced Analytics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can help organizations make better and more informed business decisions (including information regarding customer buying patterns) supporting managers to develop R strategies 	Kamble et al., 2018; Koh et al., 2019; Oztemel & Gursev, 2020; Koot et al.,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help to increase the quantity, quality and timeliness of circularity-related information exchanged between SC partners, enabling greater levels of visibility, trust and collaboration and reducing related uncertainties • The growing need for data tends to impact the selection of suppliers, as companies should look for partners who are capable of providing the necessary information and with the required quality and punctuality 	2021; Maheshwari, 2021; Rad et al., 2022
Artificial intelligence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributes to reduce uncertainty and enhance SC resilience; • Map data from the product usage by end-users and to propose adequate R strategy • Transparency, ensuring last-mile delivery, offering personalized solutions to both upstream and downstream stakeholders, minimizing the impact of disruption and facilitating an agile procurement strategy 	Acerbi et al., 2021; Modgil et al., 2022
Cloud based computer systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Favors collaboration by facilitating information sharing, supporting the development of circular supply chain strategies 	Cegielski et al., 2012; Xu et al., 2018; Koh et al., 2019; Oztemel & Gursev, 2020; Rad et al., 2022
Distributed Ledger Technology (Blockchain)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributes to enhance visibility across the entire product lifecycle, • Increase data security; data traceability, transparency, and management; 	Kouhizadeh et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2022.
Internet of Things (IoT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IoT impacts the security and privacy of SC partners; • Enhance real-time visibility • Can increase operational efficiency, cost saving during production process and optimize product recovery operations 	Kamble et al., 2018; Koh et al., 2019; Rad et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2018
Robots	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase operational efficiency and flexibility • Enable CE strategies like WEEE handling in recovery materials and disassembly processes 	Kamarul Bahrin et al., 2016; Renteria et al., 2019; Álvarez-de-los-Mozos et al., 2020; Oztemel & Gursev, 2020
3D printing / Additive manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate the adoption of circular-friendly designs • Facilitate the implementation of circular concepts by using reclaimed and recycled materials and/or more sustainable materials 	Despeisse et al., 2017; Kamarul Bahrin et al., 2016; Koh et al., 2019; Rad et al., 2022
Drones and Automated vehicles [AVs]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Important tool to facilitate reverse logistics 	Bányai, 2022; Mahroof et al., 2021

5. SOTECIN FACTORY FRAMEWORK

According to the findings in literature, the SoTeIn Factory framework is based on 2 main frameworks:

- **Conceptual framework:** this layer is based on the main concepts we have investigated and aims to explain how these concepts are interlinked. Moreover, each is considered as a variable connected with the others and we have identified a set of actions to be taken into consideration when implementing this approach. This framework was removed for confidentiality purposes. It will be updated after a scientific publication.
- **Operational framework:** this layer is based on the identification of the most important actors involved in the overall CE approach and identification of the relationship between them. Based on the Rs strategies, it was possible to identify how these actors collaborate each other, which activities they should carry on for each of the R strategy. This framework aims to help stakeholders to help implementation of the Rs. This framework was removed for confidentiality purposes. It will be updated after a scientific publication.

5.1 Conceptual Framework

This section and all its sub-sections were removed for confidentiality purposes. It will be updated after a scientific publication.

5.2 Operational framework

This section and all its sub-sections were removed for confidentiality purposes. It will be updated after a scientific publication.

5.2.1. Actors and processes

6. SOTECIN FACTORY VALUE CHAINS

In this section we give a short overview of the selected value chains for which specific challenges on circularity will be defined along the project. Here we give an overview based on what is available in literature and what was collected from partners (in particular Metabolic and BWCon) in terms of best practices for CE. This collection of challenges was guided by the dimensions identified in the previous sections, namely when searching for literature and case studies the dimensions considered where related to R strategies, collaboration, role of technologies and resilience. It is clear that given the complexity of each value chain, at this stage of the project the aim was not to be exhaustive but to give some examples that can be inspirational for the work in WP3 to trigger the definition of specific challenges.

6.1 Fashion value chain

6.1.1. Value chain at a glance

The fashion ecosystem includes transformation of natural (e.g. cotton, flax, wool, leather), manmade and artificial (synthetic polyester and viscose) fibres into yarns and fabrics, production of yarns, home textiles, technical textiles, clothing and footwear. The ecosystem is particularly competitive in high-end clothing and technical textile for automotive applications, medical textile, agro-textile and protective clothing, footwear and accessories. Most companies operate in complex value chains, making them dependent on external supplies, which can easily be disrupted. Apparel consumption expected to double per capita between 2014 and 2030 and the sector's rapid increase in size which has placed an unprecedented stress on natural resources (EC, 2021).

The ecosystem has been hard hit by the shutdown of retail outlets. In 2020 textile & clothing, footwear and leather goods retail sales decreased by 24.4%. EU turnover for textiles decreased by 9.3% and the decline in the clothing industry was 17.7%. Demand for leather is weak and only very special market segments are doing better (luxury sector, automotive and furniture). Turnover in the tanning sector declined by close to 25% (Eurostat and EC, 2021). The footwear sector has seen a further decrease in sales as a result of the second lockdown in many Member States. Turnover for the footwear sector is estimated to decline by 30%. The manufacture of nonwovens, which is a key raw material for face masks and medical gowns, has been more resilient. In particular, demand for materials used to fight the pandemic had strong growth rates. The most significant growth rate for nonwovens in 2020 was observed in nonwovens for medical use (+118.0%). In contrast, major declines were recorded in the sales of nonwovens materials to the construction and automotive markets.

6.1.2 Current challenges

Competitiveness challenges are linked to a strong environmental footprint. In particular for what concerns the implementation of CE and resilience in the fashion sector we have collected the following challenges:

- In the design for CE it is necessary to Influence designers to think clothes materials to enable CE, i.e. making them easily separable at the end of their life;
- Reuse waste textiles as a secondary raw material in other sectors (i.e. as isolation for construction of buildings)

- Reuse can request processes like cleaning process, or new platforms for sharing offer and demand
- Mitigation of microplastics in water, and land caused by textile washing processes.
- Resource consumption continues to increase because of increasing production. Fast fashion consumes large amount of resources of low quality bringing high level of pollution, while luxury products are based on precious raw materials that in some cases might give environmental problems.
- Problems at supply chain level, since most of the fashion brands exploit an unequal system using low and middle income countries.
- At logistics level, there is a lack of 'larger and smarter' sorting facilities to enable cheap deliveries of final products as well of used quality clothes and shoes.
- As for the materials used in fashion sector, there is a high level of blended fibres prevent recyclability with current technologies.
- Extending the active life of garments through changes in consumer mindsets, design, use and reuse of products and materials is one of the core sectoral challenges.
- Significant amount of waste generated during production processes - e.g. dyeing materials wrong colour contribute to approximately 10% of pre-consumer waste.
- Changing consumer behaviour during purchasing, usage and end-of-life phase.
- For production processes it is necessary to support revamping of machines for traceability, to reduce material by products and waste along production (i.e. water dispersion during tanning, use of textile 3D printing, ...),
- Use of recycled materials from other sectors like extend the use of recycling plastic bottles into polyester fabrics
- Increase collaboration along supply chain to reduce the use of dangerous substances (i.e. potassium permanganate from denim garments), tracking quality of raw materials arriving from distant countries like China, Egypt, traceability for optimizing logistics (i.e. waste recovery, packaging reduction, ..), problem with several types of certification
- Need of a digital product passport – necessary to define what to tell and where to take the data from.

6.2 Agri-food value chain

6.2.1 Value chain at a glance

The agri-food ecosystem covers all operators in the food supply chain (farmers, food industry, food retail and wholesale, and food service) and their suppliers of inputs and services (seeds, pesticides, fertiliser, machinery, packaging, repair, transport, finance, advice and logistics).

SMEs are the backbone of the agri-food ecosystem since 99% of food and drink enterprises are SMEs, representing 60% of employment and 47.5% of turnover. Only 1% of food and drink companies are leading large enterprises; they however employ 40% of the workforce and generate 52.5% of turnover of the sector (Eurostat and EC, 2021).

While trusted for providing high quality and safe products, the agri-food ecosystem has longstanding vulnerabilities. Large food companies are globally competitive (yet in need of skilled workforce and innovation). Innovation research is often dispersed, R&D investment comparatively low. Digitalisation

is increasing, but still insufficient. Farmers have lower incomes compared to other economic actors and face uncertainty, linked to weather, price variation or income volatility. Food retail needs to restructure and adapt to new consumer trends. The ecosystem showed resilience during the COVID-19 crisis (no food shortages) but suffered from sudden changes in demand patterns, disappearance of key outlets, disruption to cross-border trade and shortage of workers. In Q2 2020 food industry output decreased by 9.6% (but some producers, dependant on hospitality, faced higher losses). The need to adapt working conditions and logistics has increased costs. Food service operators face high uncertainty and many may not recover. The agri-food ecosystem is facing problems related to the degradation of natural capital, on which it is based, resulting in spillovers affecting biodiversity and environmental quality at large. Some protectionist national measures may also introduce obstacles in the Single Market negatively affecting the agri-food ecosystem. For example, by providing more advantageous and competitive marketing conditions for domestic food products, discriminating against similar imported products (EC, 2021).

6.2.2 Current challenges

In particular for what concerns the implementation of circular economy and resilience in the agri-food sector we have collected the following challenges:

- Food wastage and loss: along the supply chain-food loss occurs in during initial stages while food waste occurs later-on.
- Environmental pollution due to agriculture like nutrients run-off: an example is given by the Baltic sea where there is an oversupply of nutrient run-off from surrounding agricultural land. Many farmers, farmer organizations and food businesses are working hard to develop and implement methods to reduce the loads of excess nutrients that end up in the Baltic Sea. Despite these efforts, there is still a great need to reduce nutrient runoff from arable land and take further steps to capture and cycle human waste, crop residues and manure back into the system where possible.
- Food traceability: need to track and trace at different stages of the value chain (from farmer to final customer) like use of nutrients, status of the plants during growing phase, status of the final products on the shelves, the use of materials in agriculture.
- Need of adaptive capacity for achieving a sustainable food system that must be built into both biophysical aspects of the system (through the preservation of biodiversity, maintenance of healthy soil systems, maintenance of buffering capacity in water bodies, etc.)
- Need of adaptive capacity in terms of socioeconomic aspects of the system for knowledge transfer and increase organisational capacity of farmers, etc.
- Develop a global dataset of enabling policies of nature-based solutions is missing, hindering knowledge sharing and effective policy action.
- New capability to multi-stakeholder involvement and a complex transition since the current global food system contributes to the transgression of several planetary boundaries.
- Transforming the food system by implementing practices that help to regenerate ecosystems for tackling the most urgent environmental challenges today.
- Engagement of all stakeholders (i.e. farmers and suppliers) to ensure a holistic approach for mapping opportunities and tackling key barriers.
- The use of inappropriate economic or marketing methods in convincing customers can be dangerous: people follow complex and seemingly chaotic mechanisms to make decisions and

adopt behaviours, with a multitude of factors influencing these. When following conventional economic or marketing models, most interventions to change consumer behaviour focus on providing facts and information. They may make use of controversial, reprimanding, or shocking messages to reach their audiences. However, consumers often shun these negative narratives and disregard information related to things they don't care about or feel unable to change.

- Collaborate with other sectors (like plastic and packaging) for cross-sectorial solutions.

6.3 Plastic value chain

6.3.1 Value chain at a glance

Plastic is an essential material in our economy and daily lives. Due to its versatility, plastics have been used across all economic sectors with a variety of functions. To meet the ever-growing demand, global plastics production has increased in recent decades, and in 2019 hit an annual peak of 368 million metric tons. Europe is a key region when it comes to the production of plastics, accounting for around 16% of production, totalling 57.2 million metric tons in 2021 (an increase of 6% from the previous year) (Eurostat and EC, 2021). In 2020, European plastics production decreased due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The majority of Europe's plastic production is fossil-based.

As an important part of modern life, plastics make many of the things we do possible. Plastics have been connected to innovations that help tackle a number of the challenges facing by the society, such as: the development of more energy efficient buildings and houses; fuel savings in all transportation means through lighter materials and components; and combined with additive manufacturing technologies, bio-compatible plastic materials can save human lives by enabling medical innovation.

However, in the way it is currently produced, used and discarded plastics have serious negative effects on the environment and human health. Almost 26 million tonnes of plastic waste are generated in Europe every year and around 80% of marine litter is plastic. The EU is acting to tackle plastic pollution and marine litter to accelerate the transition to a circular and resource-efficient plastics economy.

6.3.2 Current challenges

A set of challenges have been identified in terms of circular economy and resilience in the plastics sector:

- Use more recycled plastics in order to reduce dependence on the extraction of fossil fuels for plastics production and decrease CO₂ emissions;
- Develop alternative types of raw material (e.g. bio-based plastics or plastics produced from carbon dioxide or methane) offering the same functionality as traditional plastics with potentially lower environmental impacts;
- Design and produce plastics and products containing plastics that consider the adoption of different R strategies, such as reuse, repair (designed to allow greater durability) and high-quality recycling;
- Improve design to make plastics and plastic products easier to recycle;
- Develop policies and standards to support more sustainable and safer consumption and production patterns for plastics;

- Promote improved ways to collect plastic waste, ensuring the quality of the inputs to the recycling industry;
- Develop technologies to support sorting and recycling plastic.

6.4 Packaging value chain

6.4.1 Value chain at a glance

The packaging sector is the industry that deals with the design and production of packaging products, including everything from shelf displays to boxes used during transport to protect goods. The packaging industry aims to create secure packaging to keep products safe from damage (including bubble wrap, moulded foam) and facilitate transportation; and also support sales, showing products with appealing visuals to stimulate consumer interest, with a more aesthetic orientation.

The main materials used in the packaging industry are plastics, paper/paperboard and derivatives. Packaging is one of the main users of virgin materials as 40% of plastics and 50% of paper used in the EU is destined for packaging. On average, each European generates almost 180 kg of packaging waste per year (Eurostat and EC, 2021).

6.4.2 Current challenges

A set of challenges have been identified for the development of circular value chains in the packaging sector:

- Reduce the amount of virgin materials used in the packaging industry – increase the use of recycled materials;
- Design and produce packaging that consider the adoption of different R strategies, especially reuse and refill;
- Need to innovate on the use of new materials for packaging;
- Develop sustainable packaging adapted to e-commerce;
- Combine packaging design with innovative transportation modes (drones, autonomous vehicles);
- Use of digital technologies in the packaging production (e.g. 3D printing, digital printing, robotics);
- Policies and regulation tend to make pressure on packaging industry towards greater sustainability.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this task T2.1, we have investigated models available in literature related to CE, its barriers and challenges. From this review emerged the need for developing models and frameworks to study the interrelations between CE and Resilience, having technologies (with a particular focus on digital technologies) as enablers and collaboration as mediating factor. The formalisation of these relationships is even more important when dealing with social innovation, where the traditional business relationships between suppliers and focal companies, consumer and focal companies need to take into consideration an active role of all these stakeholders with the expectation of a positive social impact of business.

For this reason, we have developed a 2-level framework for strategically link the foundational concepts of the project and propose an operational model to extended supply chain (SC) processes. The overall conceptualisation of the new framework was based on defining relationships between the different dimensions of the SoTeIn Factory with particular focus on how Circular Economy (CE) is linked to the concept of resilience and how it can be supported by technologies and collaboration.

The conceptual and operational frameworks were designed in such a way to define mechanisms where social and industrial actors can pool resources through collaborative mechanisms, including knowledge, creativity and technologies. Special attention was given to different trust building mechanisms and to the use of technologies to support these. Moreover, this deliverable aims to define how the SoTeIn Factory framework can increase our understanding of how CE can help companies to face resilience, defined as the capability to face disruptive events, while improving social, environmental, and economic outcomes of the industrial value chains. This work is the foundation for the definition of the missions and challenges in the 4 value chains along the whole project.

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